

JURISPRUDENCE

CONSTITUTIONAL CONTROL IN THE REPUBLIC OF ALBANIA

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Abstract

In this paper, will be dealt with the history of the birth and development of constitutional control in Albania. From the analysis of the organizational structure of the Constitutional Court, it results that Albania has represented the European model of constitutional control since 1998. At the same time, the jurisdiction and the authorized parties that can initiate a case in the Constitutional Court of Republic of Albania have been elaborated.

The methodology applied consists of the historical method, descriptive method, legal analytical method and comparative method.

From the research, it has been established that the Constitutional Court of Albania has faced several constitutional and legal obstacles during practice, which in some cases have resulted in its efficient dysfunction from an organizational point of view but also in the exercise of the powers that have been recognized by the Constitution, therefore in the year 2016 constitutional reform was carried out.

Keywords: jurisdiction, authorized party, constitutionality, constitutional amendments.

1. The birth and development of constitutional control in Albania

The activity of the Constitutional Court in Albania is divided into two stages: the first stage includes the years 1991-1998 during which it functioned on the basis of the Main Constitutional Provisions, while the second stage includes the time after the entry into force of the new Constitution of November 28, 1998 and the Law "On the organization and functioning of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Albania" in 2000 (Constitutional Court of Republic of Albania , 2020).

The Constitutional Court in the Republic of Albania (CCRA) is not part of the ordinary judicial system (Zagonjari, XH., et al., 2011). It has special jurisdiction to review the constitutionality of laws and other normative acts, while guaranteeing respect for the constitution and making its final interpretation (Law No. 76/2016, 2016).

The CCRA has encountered several constitutional and legal obstacles during its practice, which in some cases have resulted in its ineffective functioning from an organizational point of view or in its ineffectiveness in exercising the powers granted to it by the Constitution, therefore the constitution was amended in part eight - the Constitutional Court and also the Law "On the Organization and Functioning of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Albania" of 2000, which was amended and supplemented by law no. 99/2016 and law no. 45/2021 (Justice system reform strategy, 2015).

These constitutional amendments constitute the foundation of a profound reform in legal and

institutional terms, consequently strengthening the rule of law in the Republic of Albania.

2. Jurisdiction of the CCRA

As a very important institution in the constitutional system of every democratic state, the Constitutional Court guarantees the application of fundamental principles by all constitutional bodies, in order to strengthen the rule of law. It accomplishes this mission through constitutional control (Vorpsi, A., et. al., 2019). Thus, it turns out that constitutional control has an impact on strengthening the rule of law.

While some constitutional courts simply adjudicate the constitutionality of legislation, others are authorized to decide on a variety of additional questions, some of them quite politically sensitive. In addition to the core function of deciding constitutional issues, a number of constitutional courts in Central and Eastern Europe have jurisdiction over matters relating to elections, referendums, impeachment of the president, and the legality of political parties (Horowitz, 2006). The CCRA, in article 131 regulates the jurisdiction of the Constitutional Court, which concerns the control of the constitutionality of laws, international agreements prior to ratification, normative acts of central and local bodies, the resolution of disputes of competence between state powers, the constitutionality of political parties and the control of the activity they exercise, the verification of elections and referendums, issues of eligibility and incompatibility of the exercise of the function of the President of the Republic and of deputies, and in particular the sphere of protection of fundamental

rights and freedoms of individuals (Constitution of the Republic of Albania, 1998).

A special regulation with the constitutional amendments of 2016 is provided for the protection of human rights and freedoms, where it finally judges the complaints of individuals against any act of public authority or judicial decision that violates fundamental rights and freedoms, after exhausting all effective legal remedies for the protection of these rights (Law No. 76/2016, 2016). This is because previously the 1998 Constitution only guaranteed protection for the right to due process. The idea was that since every individual's right is reviewed by ordinary courts, only constitutional recourse for the control of the right to due process, which means the judicial process, is sufficient for other rights to be ensured (Kryeziu, 2022, p. 104).

The object of constitutional review in the CCRA under article 140/4 and article 115 may also be (Constitution of the Republic of Albania, 1998): "the decision of the Assembly to dismiss the President of the Republic; the decision to dismiss judges of the Supreme Court and the decision of the Council of Ministers to dismiss mayors of communes or municipalities."

With the constitutional amendments implemented through Law No. 137/2015, article 3 stipulates that the jurisdiction of the Constitutional Court be expanded to include the examination of issues related not only to incompatibilities in the exercise of the functions of the President of the Republic, members of parliament, and officials of the bodies provided for in the Constitution, but also to the verification of their election. There are other constitutional provisions where, after the verification carried out by the Constitutional Court, it must express its opinion on the constitutionality of investigative procedures carried out by various state bodies (Vorpsi, A., et. al., 2019, p. 117) such as cases: when the Court finds incompatibility in the exercise of the duties of a deputy, when one of the conditions of the deputy's ineligibility is confirmed; when verifying the procedures of eligibility or incompatibility in the exercise of the functions of the President of the Republic, when it definitively confirms the fact of the inability of the President of the Republic to exercise his duties for more than sixty (60) days, when declaring the dismissal of the President of the Republic from office, as a result of the confirmation of his guilt, when dismissing a member of the High Judicial Council from office, the General Prosecutor, member of the High Prosecutorial Council, The High Inspector of Justice", etc. Also, based on article 127 of the Constitution, the declaration of the end of the mandate of a constitutional judge is another type of constitutional trial, which is made by decision of the Constitutional Court. In all these aforementioned cases, the Constitutional Court does not repeal any legal norm. Attention should be paid to the constitutional amendments adopted in 2016, which specify the situation when the Constitutional Court "is set in motion to review a law on the revision of the Constitution, approved by the Assembly", which is limited and exercises control only over the observance of the procedure provided for by the Constitution (Law No. 76/2016, 2016).

3. Authorized parties in the CCRA

As a rule, proceedings before the Constitutional Court are based on the respective request submitted by a specific constitutional subject or by applicants who must prove their legitimacy (Sadushi, 2012, p. 64). Thus, the CCRA, with the constitutional amendments implemented in 2016, has expanded the number of authorized parties who, at their request, can activate the Constitutional Court, which are: "state bodies such as the President of the Republic; the Prime Minister; no less than one-fifth of the deputies; Ombudsman; the President of the High State Audit; any court, any Commissioner established by law for the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution, the High Judicial Council and the High Prosecutorial Council, local government bodies", while other authorized parties are also "bodies of religious communities; political parties; organizations and individuals" (Law No. 76/2016, 2016).

With the constitutional amendments, only the Commissioner established by law for the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution and the President of the High State Audit were added, which were not previously foreseen by the constitutional norms approved in 1998.

The President of the Republic, the Prime Minister, one-fifth of the deputies and the Ombudsman are bearers of the public interest, whose interest is "the protection of the normative system and state-forming principles such as constitutionalism, the rule of law, democracy, human dignity, social equality, etc. as set forth in the Constitution, is not conditioned by the verification of the existence of an interest in the matter under consideration" (Decesion no.18, 2018). The distinguishing feature of a request initiated by any of the aforementioned public office holders is that we have an abstract and objective control of the law, which is related to the respect of constitutional principles and the proper functioning of the rule of law (Decesion no.18, 2018).

As for other authorized parties, including the President of the High State Audit Office; any court, any Commissioner established by law for the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution, the High Judicial Council and the High Prosecutorial Council, local government bodies, bodies of religious communities; political parties; organizations and individuals" conditions the right of the subject to submit a request with the possession of a concrete constitutionally protected interest (Vorpsi, A., et. al., 2019). Further, the legal norms have been regulated in detail, providing for each of the authorized parties the procedure to be carried out before the Constitutional Court, which includes the authorized parties, the subject of the appeal, the criteria that must be met by each party, and the review by the Constitutional Court (Law No. 99/2016, 2016).

As for elaboration, in the case where the Constitution of Albania has provided for individuals as authorized parties before the Constitutional Court, further legal provisions have specified that an individual includes a natural or legal person, a subject of private and public law, as well as determining that

the object of the appeal may be the law, the normative act or the decisions of the High Judicial Council and the High Prosecutorial Council, continuing further and specifying the criteria that must be met in this case for the exercise of an individual constitutional appeal as well as the review by the Constitutional Court (Law No. 99/2016, 2016).

Thus, with the expansion of authorized parties, it has been possible to prevent and reduce violations of constitutional provisions.

Conclusion

Albania has applied the European model of constitutional review, establishing the Constitutional Court as an independent body that is not part of the judiciary and has special jurisdiction over the constitutionality of laws and other normative acts, while guaranteeing respect for the constitution and making its final interpretation.

The fundamental constitutional reform of 2016 had an impact on the aspects of the organization, functioning and jurisdiction of the Constitutional Court. These changes provided, among others, for the expansion of individual constitutional appeals, which aim to provide greater protection for individuals against acts of public authority that guarantee constitutional protection of all human rights and freedoms.

As a result, the Constitutional Court of Albania with its jurisdiction has become a very important institution in the constitutional system of Albania as a democratic state, as it guarantees the application of fundamental principles by all constitutional bodies in order to strengthen the rule of law.

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